

DOI :

Role of Transgender in Indian and Japanese Cinema Industry

Chitta Ranjan Malik

Former Researcher of Japanese Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi.

ABSTRACT

Cinema Industry is the main vehicle for raising public awareness of and participation in local and social issues by drawing them into the public eye and collective consciousness. Cinema is a powerful force for social change. Like all other forms of art, film is a part of social realism. Transnationalism in cinema may also be seen as a production and consumption strategy, in addition to ideologies, genres, and aesthetics. It asserts that ethnic passing, which is more common in popular culture, highlights questions surrounding ethnicity, transnational capital, transcultural flows, and globalization at the start of the twenty-first century by mobilising the notion of passing in transgender practice. Transgender people are usually portrayed by the mainstream media, particularly on television and films, as dismal jokes. India, a nation seen to be sexually conservative, has a long history of gender-variant identities. On the other hand, Male to Female (MtF) transgender culture is the most noticeable minority queer culture in India and is likely to face further marginalization. Indian films have often influenced a great deal of public opinion. A nationwide conversation has been sparked by films like Rang De Basanti (2006), which have forced the people to think about significant concerns. In Indian films, members of the LGBTQIA+ community are freely and inclusively represented. In Japan, a nation with a long and well-documented history of transgenderism, biological males and females who choose to live their lives to varying degrees in the gender considered to be 'opposite' to their birth sex are known as transgendered persons. The phenomenal popularity of the Carrousel performers in Tokyo nightclubs has been likened to the arrival of the black ships for the LGBT community in Japan.

Keywords: Cinema Industry, Globalization, LGBTQIA+, Transcultural, Transnationalism,

INTRODUCTION

The cinema Industry is the main source of information on social issues that affect communities and local areas, helping to raise awareness of these issues and educate the public about them. The movie theatre is a powerful catalyst for social change. Like other artistic mediums, film is both a vehicle and an element of social authenticity. Movies have a subtle impact on society's thought processes. The film is a part of social realism, much like all other art forms.

The most powerful weapon is the movie's profound impact on society and its way of thinking. Gender roles are warped as a result of false gender stereotypes in the

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	DOI: Article No - TVRV00057

Address for correspondence :			
Dr. Chitta Ranjan Malik, Former Researcher of Japanese Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi.			
E-mail- chittaranjanju2@gmail.com			
ORCID ID: 0009-0006-6951-6752			
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For reprints contact: voiceforvoiceless2013@gmail.com			
Received	Reviewed	Accepted	Published
02-Feb.-2024	27-Mar.-2024	22-Apr.-2024	10-Jun.-2024
Volume	Issue	June	ISSN
No. 6	No. 1	2024	2583-1852(P), 2584-0878(O)
How to Cite this Article: Malik, Chitta Ranjan; Role of Transgender in Indian and Japanese Cinema Industry. <i>THE THIRD VOICE REALITY AND VISION</i> . 2024. Vol No-6. Issue No-1. June. Pp: 52-55. DOI			

media, as films are a medium through which society forms beliefs about gender and identity. This appears restricted and crowded to viewers. Within the film and cinema studies sectors, there has been a growing appeal for the notion of contesting the national cinema framework with that of transnational cinema. In terms of production and consumption methods, transnationalism in film may be seen as a synthesis of ideologies, genres, and aesthetics.

Transnationalism, however, has been claimed to only reinstall the nation inside a larger, pan-national framework rather than really displace it, despite its promise to transcend the national. It is argued that ethnic passing, which is increasingly common in popular culture (think of the three ethnically Chinese actresses who play Japanese geishas in the film *Memoirs of a Geisha*), raises issues of ethnicity, transnational capital, transcultural flows, and globalization at the start of the twenty-first century through the use of the concept of passing in transgender practice.

In India, transgender communities were not given much thought until the early 21st century. The highly acclaimed film *Ardhanari* (directed by Santhosh Souparnika in 2012) brought attention to the terrible circumstances of the transgender community in 2011. The mainstream media usually depicts transsexual people as dismal jokes, especially on television and cinema.

Transgender in the Indian Cinema Industry

India, which is perceived as a sexually conservative country, has historically produced a large number of gender nonconforming individuals. However, Male to Female (MtF) transgender culture is the most noticeable minority queer culture in India and is expected to face even more marginalization. Individuals who identify as transgender have faced decades of persecution, harassment, and prejudice from society, and in Indian culture, they are barely accepted. Indian films have often influenced a great deal of public opinion. Some would even go so far as to say that by making individuals think about things they would otherwise dismiss, they mould people's thought processes. Films such as *Rang De Basanti* (2006) have provoked a national conversation by making viewers consider significant problems.

In an industry that is so powerful and influential, the portrayal of transgender people is like a closet full of skeletons that no one talks about. Since their first prominent appearance in the Hindi film *Kunwara Baap*,

eunuchs have mostly been seen as sources of comic relief and ridicule. Eunuchs are always raucous and unruly, never human, and they always dress in bright colours. They are objectified as dazzling sidekicks. It is time to put an end to the current negative, stereotypical representation of transgender people in Indian movies. Consequently, Bollywood is reverse-modernizing its way to the forefront of this degradation.

Eunuchs and other non-binary identities have often been portrayed in films as antagonists out to rape and castrate as many men as possible, or as comic relief. Most middle-class and upper-class Indian families who have not engaged with LGBTQA+ persons have surely developed certain preconceptions about the transgender community over time. They have therefore stigmatized their community, friends, and relatives. *Agneepath* (2012), a film by Dharma Productions, had transgender actors in a small role as machete-wielding assassins. Karan Malhotra. In the 2011 Bollywood film *Murder-2* (Mohit Suri, 2011), actor Prashant Narayanan played the role of eunuch and insane killer and tormentor Dheeraj Pandey.

The film vividly details Dheeraj's agony, yet it never once shows his psychological suffering. We see a guy abusing young women, but we never get to see inside his head or what drives him. It strengthens the stereotype that transgender individuals are wicked, cold-blooded murderers if not just absurd jokers. This has a profound effect on viewers' perceptions and generates a wide generalisation that applies to everyone. Eunuchs have provided slapstick comedic relief in a number of films.

The historical drama *Jodha Akbar* (Ashutosh Gowariker, 2008) features a Eunuch guard of the *Zenana*, which are women's quarters in Indian palaces traditionally inhabited by transgender people. The guard is used to bring lightness to sombre scenes and later plots against the Queen, incorporating both of the stereotypes of Eunuchs in Indian cinema. As a proficient assassin, Ni'ammatt the Eunuch was also highly sexualized and comical, exhibiting stereotypes and portraying a demon image.

Ms. Pakhi Sharma, better known by her stage name Bobby Darling, is the only transgender performer in India, and she has always been cast in parts like queer perverts, oddball stylists, and gay perverts. It turns out that in none of these scenarios could she articulate any basic emotions. In the scene, she is shown as the standard Eunuch, displaying her body and begging for money.

Bollywood is trying its hardest to adapt to the changing social norms. Modern Indian cinema, however, isn't scared to depict LGBTQIA+ individuals without bias, in contrast to the past, when a number of films and even television shows vilified transgender persons and depicted them as caricatures.

Transgender in the Japanese Cinema Industry

In Japan, transgenderism is a long-standing and well-documented practice in which biological males and females choose to spend their lives to varying degrees as members of the gender that is seen as 'opposite' to their natal sex. Individuals who desired to live as the other gender had few alternatives until recently. These possibilities were mostly limited to Japan's *mizushobai*, or 'water trade,' which refers to the vast world of bars, clubs, cabarets, and massage parlours in Tokyo and other major cities where transgender features may be promoted as a unique talent or performance.

In Tokyo nightclubs, the incredible success of Carrousel performers has been compared to the arrival of black ships for Japan's LGBT population. Geiboi, who were already known for their effeminate demeanour, were encouraged to adopt a more transsexual appearance. The 1960s saw an increase in the number of 'show bars' (shoba), which presented floor shows with geiboi who performed for an audience of heterosexual 'tourists,' thanks in part to Le Carrousel's influence.

One of these boys was Peter, who, at the age of fifteen, had run away from home and was playing at a show bar in Roppongi when he was seen by a scout. He later appeared in the 1969 film *Bara No Soretsu* (Funeral Parade of Roses) directed by Matsumoto Toshio. Peter later starred in the film *Ran*, directed by Akira Kurosawa, and is now a well-known figure on television. Peter hasn't stopped dressing differently.

Kumi Kobata and Naoko Oigami were rare in Japan, a country where independent filmmakers were just as uncommon as female directors and producers. When asked how they met, they shook their heads, joking quietly because none of them could recall. After a while, Oigami remembered seeing it in her 2006 movie 'Seagull Diner' (KamomeShokudo). Suurkitos, Kobata's film distribution company, became involved in the production as a sponsor and oversaw the Japanese release of the movie.

Over the last 10 years, the collaboration has made five films, the most recent of which is 'Close-Knit' (KareragaHonki de Amu Toki Ha), which features a topic

that is also unique in Japan. The story of a transgender lady, the person who loves her, and the young daughter who enters their lives is presented in 'Close-Knit,' which delves into an extremely topical topic. Rinko, a transsexual woman, lives with Makio (Kenta Kiritani, another immensely popular actor in Japan), who accepts her unconditionally. Rinko is played by Toma Ikuta, one of the country's most popular young male stars.

Tomo (Rinka Kakihara), Makio's very little daughter, comes at her uncle's door after her emotionally troubled sister departs with a partner. Rinko, Makio's girlfriend, warmly greets her and begins caring for the child. As she comes to know the little girl, Rinko is motivated by memories of her mother's love for her when she was a boy and discovers more about her maternal instincts. Tomo matures into the kid that Rinko longs for but will never be able to have. When the girl's biological mother returned from her journey to fetch her kid, a decision must be made. The Transgender Monster is an examination of the use of gender-transgressive murderers in horror and slasher films. But this eerie portrayal is more well-known from films like *Psycho* and *Silence of the Lambs*.

CONCLUSION

The movie is seen to be a potent tool for communication and social change. Undoubtedly, the film industry has played a significant role in the growth of the LGBT community in India. In a nation like India, where films have the power to shape the opinions of the vast majority of people, realistic films that depict the transgender community will undoubtedly have a profoundly good impact on people's perceptions. Indian cinema is renowned for its terrible portrayal of the transgender community. The variety of transgender experiences in Japan should not be overlooked, nor should the lives and experiences of the 'other' transgender individuals in Japan be seen as a side note to the development of the medical model, regardless of how important the latest developments may be for some. There's more to cinema than just having fun. The development also has to be emphasized.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable

Author's contributions

Author himself responsible for the first manuscript draft. Author has contributed to subsequent drafts and approved the final version.

Funding

No funding received for this study

Availability of data and materials

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study

DECLARATIONS

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The author declares no competing interests.

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